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Editor(s):	Revaz Berozashvili, German Castellanos (ACC)
Author(s)/Contributor(s):	Joss Armstrong (LMI)
	Guillermo Bielsa, Juan Sanchez (TSA)
	Jesús Gutiérrez, Vladica Sark (IHP)
	Israel Koffman, Baruch Globen (REL)
	J. Pérez-Romero, O. Sallent, J. Sánchez-González, A. Umbert (UPC)
	Miguel Catalán-Cid, Esteban Municio (i2CAT)
	Josep Xavier Salvat, Jose A. Ayala, Hans van der Veen (NEC)
	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
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List of Acronyms

5GPPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
B5G	Beyond 5G
COTS	Commercial-Off-The-Shelf
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CU	Central Unit
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DPD	Digital-Pre-Distortion
DU	Distributed Unit
EDP	Extended Data Processing
ET	Envelope Tracking
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
GA	Grant Agreement
GPU	Graphics processing unit
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and communication technology
IM	Innovation Manager
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
ISG	Industry Specification Group
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NDT	Network Digital Twin
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEX	Operational Expenditures
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSS	Operational Support System
PA	Power Amplifier
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIA	Research & Innovation Action
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface

RRH	Remote Radio Head
RU	Radio Unit
SAM	Serviceable Available Market
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SOM	Serviceable Obtainable Market
TAM	Total Addressable Market
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership
UC	Use Case
UPF	User Plane Function
VP	Value Proposition
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity

Executive Summary

This document, BeGREEN D6.2, is the “Interim Report on Exploitation”, reporting the work of BeGREEN Task 6.4. It includes details about the innovation management methodology applied within BeGREEN and draws some initial conclusions and results obtained during the 18 months of the project. This report evolves the exploitation plan of BeGREEN D6.1 [1].

This document also provides an updated exploitation plan for individual Parties, and an updated joint exploitation plan. Particularly, it identifies and summarises the exploitable outcomes from the project. The methodologies for analysing these exploitable outcomes are as well described.

This document comprises 5 chapter. Following the Executive Summary, the following chapters are:

- Chapter 1 introduces the document and provides the context of the innovation objectives defined in the BeGREEN Grant Agreement (GA).
- Chapter 2 elaborates the project’s innovation goals, innovation methodology and innovation assessment.
- Chapter 3 presents the exploitation strategy, methodology applied by each partner, and the value proposition and the Lean Canvases used by each partner.
- Chapter 4 summarizes the main exploitable outcomes identified in BeGREEN and introduces updated individual plans and joint exploitation plans.
- Chapter 5 presents an updated market analysis of the commercialization of the BeGREEN innovation results.
- Chapter 6 is the conclusion and summary.

The exploitation goals of BeGREEN are consistent with the scope of the project SNS Stream A call SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-01, of type RIA action, with results typically of TRL 3-4 (with some limited results of TRL 5) maturity, with significant additional innovation and commercialization efforts required, beyond the results of this project, for true commercial exploitation.

1 Introduction

BeGREEN D6.2 reports the work carried out in the context of BeGREEN Task 6.4 (T6.4) and documents the results of the activities undertaken during BeGREEN's first project 18 months, implementing the initial phase of the exploitation plan defined in BeGREEN D6.1 [1].

BeGREEN T6.4, entitled "Exploitation of Results", includes different aspects of identifying and promoting the impact of the BeGREEN project. Accordingly, what unites the two elements named in the task is that each one of them deals with the impact of the project. These two elements are:

- **Exploitation strategies** promote activities aimed at exploiting the project results in technological, commercial, and scientific ways, thus enlarging the direct impact of the project in these three realms. Exploitation is fundamental to any kind of impact of the project, as it describes the further use of all results, insights, and collaborations, which is necessary for technologies being further developed and adopted at a larger scale and thus having further impact, e.g., on environmental sustainability. BeGREEN D6.2 presents the main exploitable assets created through BeGREEN as well as the exploitation activities and outcomes by project partners.
- **Business plans and business modelling** are closely related to commercial exploitation. A technological innovation and a related idea for commercial exploitation needs a good and fitting business model to succeed. 5G technology does not only enable an immense range of new applications to be built and services to be offered, it also substantially reshapes the ecosystem in which actors operate, necessitating strong business models that also take this into account, and provide commercial justification in further investing in these exploitable results to mature them to suitable TRL for commercial markets.

1.1 Exploitation objectives

In WP6, there are defined 2 objectives that are linked to BeGREEN D6.2:

- **O6.4** Foster Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) creation and handle them in the most effective way among consortium partners.
- **O6.5** Devise and execute an exploitation plan and provide guidelines for future industrialization processes of the technologies and solutions realized during the project.

The following chapters and sections, BeGREEN exploitation status and activities in the first year, and focusing on the BeGREEN D6.2 are discussed.

1.2 Document structure

This document comprises 5 chapters. Following the Executive Summary and Introduction, the following chapters are:

- Chapter 2 provides information about the project’s innovation goals, innovation methodology and innovation assessment.
- Chapter 3 presents the exploitation strategy, methodology applied by each partner, and the value proposition and the Lean Canvases used by each partner.
- Chapter 4 summarizes the main exploitable outcomes identified in BeGREEN and introduces updated individual plans and joint exploitation plans.
- Chapter 5 presents an updated market analysis of the **commercialization of the BeGREEN innovation results**.
- Chapter 6 is the conclusion and summary.

2 Innovation Goals and Methodology

The role of Innovation Manager (IM) is taken by Accelleran (ACC), and the responsible person is Mr. Revaz Berozashvili. His role is to foster innovation within the project and to ensure the work is directed to the commercial needs of the market.

2.1 Innovation methodology

The first International Standard for Innovation Management systems was published in 2019. BeGREEN will base its Innovation Management in the following documents:

- ISO Innovation Management Guidance” [2], which complements the information given in the ones listed below.
- ISO Innovation management tools and methods for innovation partnership [3], and
- ISO Innovation Management Assessment Guidance [4].

Other documents such as [5] [6] [7] [8] will be used during the lifetime of the BeGREEN Project.

The IM will assist and advise the project in best responding to emerging market opportunities. In turns, by thoroughly following the evolution of the sector, the new emerging technologies and products and the mutating needs, IM helps bringing all this inside the project and will assist the project in identifying changes in strategies and re-planning of technical activities to best fit the evolving sector.

The day-to-day methodology that will be followed by the IM will be to:

- Monitor the scientific and technological developments of the project as well as the events and the state of the art relevant to the BeGREEN technology.
- Identify the risks associated to the identification and development of an innovation, and to assess the impact of the decisions to be taken regarding a particular innovation.
- Identify the enhancements in the value proposition of the applications investigated as use cases (UCs) and generalise the added value solutions that BeGREEN offers.
- Identify creative individuals in each of the partners’ teams that can contribute to boost innovation in the project, i.e. identify champions for each of the technology areas within the project. Each champion creates and updates technology roadmaps, tracking trends and directions given published information.
- Set up specific workforces to allow creative individuals or groups of them to advance in specific areas, if needed, under the budgeted conditions.
- Create and maintain constructive discussions at the WP and project level, either during face-to-face or on-line meetings, to facilitate the appearance of innovative ideas.
- Investigate market needs in selected areas of the project, where its impact can be maximised.

2.2 Innovation assessment (period 1)

Following the methodology described in Section 2.1, we have executed an exercise that reaffirm some of the proposed decisions proposed before the project kick-started. We carried out the exercise per technical WP, and these outcomes will serve to fuel the innovation potential of the solutions that will be finally promoted in BeGREEN D6.5 (M30), entitled “Final report on dissemination, impact, and exploitation”.

- **WP2:** In WP2, BeGREEN proposes an evolved radio network that targets not only improved wireless communication’s efficiency by maximising performance but also reducing energy consumption.

BeGREEN D2.1 [9] delves into describing current energy efficient frameworks and strategies that aim to model the radio access network (RAN) that serve for identifying and quantifying the parts of this network segment that can allow for improved energy efficiency and reduced energy consumption. We provided an initial description of the proposed UCs and their specific requirements, focusing on the scenarios that are subject to study and the reference Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that will be later evaluated and captured in subsequent BeGREEN documents, together with a high-level analysis of the BeGREEN RAN architecture along with the optimization strategies that can be applied to the RAN components. BeGREEN D2.1 [9] also provided the energy control mechanisms that can be applied in a 5G disaggregated RAN and mechanisms enhanced by artificial intelligence and/or machine learning (AI/ML). A key innovation of BeGREEN will be providing energy efficiency ratings and energy scores through the Energy Efficiency Calculation rApps, this is being discussed as part of WP2 and WP4 work. BeGREEN D2.2 [10] evolved this initial architecture, reporting the further architectural work of WP2.

- **WP3:** In WP3, BeGREEN addresses multiple physical layer enhancements and new technologies that will enable improving the energy efficiency of the RAN for future wireless mobile networks. Additionally, the use of these new technologies for further enhancement of the overall network energy efficiency was investigated. This was reported in BeGREEN D3.1 [11] and BeGREEN D3.2 [12].

The work in WP3 is performed in different levels and segments of the RAN. The main reasoning behind this approach is that not all the segments have the same potential for energy efficiency optimization. Therefore, within the first period of the project (BeGREEN D3.1 [11]) the areas that have the highest potential for energy efficiency optimization as well as the possible strategies for optimization, were identified. This partially disperses the work of the different partners and limits the integration of the developed technologies. Nevertheless, their work was grouped around a few different approaches for improving the network energy efficiency, which is one of the main goals of the project.

Within the first reporting period, the potential for energy efficiency optimization of different segment of the RAN was investigated and potential areas as well as approaches were identified. This includes optimization of the channel coder/decoder, since it is one of the most energy intensive part of the DU. Additionally, CU energy consumption, as well as its potential for reducing its energy consumption was assessed. Furthermore, energy optimization approaches for the remote radio head (RRH) were identified and possible strategies proposed. Finally, it was investigated how new technologies like ISAC and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) can be used for improving the network energy efficiency. Additional information and initial results that endorse the work carried out in WP3 was reported in BeGREEN D3.2 [12].

- **WP4:** The Intelligence Plane, together with its components and interfaces, is one of the main innovations coming from WP4. The AI Engine, which exposes MLOps workflows to the RICs, could be of special interest to Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN Alliance)- aligned RIC vendors and costumers due to the actual trend of AI-driven RAN optimisations. Additionally, cross-domain AI approaches such as the one being proposed in BeGREEN, which incorporates data and optimisations from RAN, Edge, Core, Application and Sensing domains, are gaining relevance in the telecom sector [13]. In this regard, the integration of RIS/ISAC technologies and O-RAN is also of significant importance due to the relevance of these technologies in 6G definition. Finally, novel rApps/xApps proposed by BeGREEN will exploit these innovations to enhance network energy efficiency. Regarding O-RAN interfaces, we are now focusing on the A1 interface due to its versatility to incorporate policies, enrichment information and AI/ML-related workflows. This allow interaction, coordination, and conflict management between non-Real-Time (rApps) and near-Real-Time RICs (xApps), which are operations of special interest to effectively manage AI-driven automated control-

loops. On the contrary, implementation-wise, the RU control through O1 interface has lost traction in the project since RunEL's RU does not incorporate this interface and their proposed RU optimisations do not require of a non-RT control. Also, in the integration with TeraVM RAN emulator we plan to focus on A1 and E2 interfaces for demonstrating intelligent and energy efficient RU management. The results of BeGREEN WP4 were reported in BeGREEN D4.1 [14] and BeGREEN D4.2 [15].

3 Exploitation Strategies

3.1 Exploitation Outcomes Classification

As the BeGREEN project has partners ranging from academic to industrial sectors, the diversity of expertise and research goals are reflected in their exploitation strategy and activities. For example, Universities and Research Centers usually focus on exploitation activities of research items, while large companies and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) are mainly interested in commercial exploitation of products.

In case of joint exploitation, IPR protection agreements for shared outcomes will be covered as per signed Consortium Agreement sections: 8.2, 9.2, 9.4, 9.9, and also needs to be considered together with GA's article 16.

In the BeGREEN project, the outcomes have mainly been classified in the following three categories:

- **Prototype/Product.** This is the outcome delivered for developing or enhancing specific products by:
 - implementation of a prototype (stand-alone products).
 - Implementing new functions or services; or improving existing ones.
- **Research Achievement:** the outcome adds to the body of knowledge and will be delivered to academic or industry through dissemination paths.
- **Demonstrators:** the outcome that would be implemented as Demonstrators in the field or in lab environment. In BeGREEN, this category mainly includes the several UC demonstrators.

3.2 Exploitation strategy and methodology

To analyze the exploitable aspects of each solution or result of the BeGREEN project, two prevailing models for customer centric identification are considered:

1. The Value Proposition (VP) Canvas
2. The Lean Canvas

Both methodologies are presented in Sections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2. For each exploitable outcome of the BeGREEN, the following steps are followed to perform the structured analysis:

The first step for each exploitable outcome is to clarify the exploitation categories, and then to identify the analysis method as explained below.

- **Prototype/Product.** This is the outcome delivered for developing or enhancing specific products by:
 - implementation of a prototype (stand-alone products).
 - Implementing new functions or services; or improving existing ones.

For these items the Value Proposition Canvas is filled-in. Through the identification of gains, pains, and opportunities, a clear and structured value proposition statement for the outcome is provided. Then for some outcomes with more promising value propositions, the Lean Canvas methodology is applied to further analyse the exploitation potential and identify the key aspects to build the related business case. In addition, the individual exploitation plan from each partner has been described and updated associated with the exploitable outcomes of their responsibility.

- **Research Achievement.** These items are analyzed in terms of their value in the individual partners' exploitation plans.
- **Demonstrators.** That is the outcome that would be implemented in the demonstrators (proof-of-concept) on an outdoor testbed or in lab environment. In BeGREEN, this category mainly includes

the several UC demonstrators. For these items, the Lean Canvas is applied to analyze the potential exploitation values. The exact scope of the demonstrations is the focus of WP5, with the initial plan reported in BeGREEN D5.1 [16]. This will be elaborated in upcoming BeGREEN D5.2 and BeGREEN D5.3.

3.2.1 Value proposition canvas methodology

The Value Proposition Canvas, as shown in Figure 3-1 and Figure 3-2, is a business model tool that helps to make sure a product or service is positioned around customers' values and needs. The primary purpose is to create a fit between the product and market. For this to happen, the Value Proposition Canvas explores deeply in the two blocks, i.e., customer profile and value map.

The customer profile described targets customer profile with key information to understand the expectation from customers regarding the results generated in BeGREEN. More specifically it contains:

- **Customer Jobs**, is about what the customer is trying to do, including the tasks customers are trying to perform, the problems they are trying to solve, and the needs they want to satisfy.
- **Pains**, encompasses everything that annoys the customer while they are performing the jobs, without applying BeGREEN solutions, such as negative experiences, challenges, risks, mistakes, etc.
- **Gains**, is all the benefits and outcomes the customer expects to achieve.

The Value Map is used to identify information regarding the features of a product or service targeting the specific customers. More specifically it contains:

- **Products and Services**: the product or a service delivered in BeGREEN to the specific Customer Profile.
- **Pain relievers**: the ways on how the BeGREEN product or service will relieve the Customer Pains.
- **Gain creators**: this involves how the product/service offers the customer added value, and what are the benefits they bring.

Figure 3-1 Value Proposition Canvas

Figure 3-2 Value Proposition Canvas

3.2.2 Lean Canvas Methodology

The Lean Canvas, as shown in Figure 3-3, is a business modelling tool to help deconstruct a start-up idea into its key and most risky assumptions. The methodology is adapted from the Business Model Canvas, with the modifications on the nine blocks in a logical order that begins from the customer's problem. More specifically it contains:

- **Problem:** the top problems the BeGREEN solution will solve.
 - **Existing Alternatives:** lists how these problems are solved today.
- **Solution:** a brief description of what the BeGREEN solution does and how it is different from the alternatives.
- **Key Metrics:** Key activities that will be measured to track the success.
- **Unique Value Proposition:** Single, clear, compelling message that states why the BeGREEN solution is different and worth paying attention.
- **Unfair Advantage:** something that cannot easily be bought or copied.
- **Channels:** Channels to be used to contact customers, promote and deliver the value promised.
- **Customer Segment:** The targeted customer profile.
 - **Early Adopters:** lists the characteristics of the ideal customer.
- **Cost Structure:** lists the fixed and variable costs for applying the solution.
- **Revenue Streams:** the main revenue streams generated from the commercialization/provision of the solution to the market.

Figure 3-3 Lean Canvas as a business modelling tool

3.2.3 Impact creation methodology

In the previous section, the classification of the exploitable outcomes and the methods for structured analysis were introduced. These exploitable outcomes would be acquired at a later stage of a project, as shown in Figure 3-4. However, to achieve greater impact creation, the impact plan needs to be considered at the beginning of research processes.

Figure 3-4 Impact creation methodology

3.3 Identification and classification of exploitation plans

The exploitable outcomes of the BeGREEN include research results, products, and integrated demonstrators for specific use cases. The exploitable outcomes list and classification is summarized in Table 3-1 with the corresponding owner(s).

Table 3-1 BeGREEN Exploitable Outcomes

#	Exploitation Outcome	Outcome Category	Methodology	Owners
1	RU power management (RU On/Off)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	REL
2	RU power management (PA management)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	REL
3	Intelligence Plane + TeraVM (RU On/Off)	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT / LMI / BT
4	Intelligence Plane	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT
5	Sensing assisted communications	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	IHP / I2CAT / NEC
6	CU HW acceleration	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / ARM
7	RIC porting into ARM	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	ACC / ARM / I2CAT
8	DU HW acceleration	Demonstrators	Lean Canvas	PW / ARM
9	ISAC / RIS	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	IHP / NEC / I2CAT
10	Saving modules such as Digital-Pre-Distortion (DPD), Envelope Tracking (ET) and Power Amplifier Blanking	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	RunEL
11	Development of rApps /xApps for optimizing Energy Efficiency in the RAN	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	I2CAT / ACC
12	CU / RIC HW acceleration. Develop xApps to achieve energy efficiently	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	ACC / I2CAT / ARM
13	DU HW Acceleration	Prototypes/Products	VP/Lean Canvas	PW
14	Assessment of energy savings in distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) scenaria	Research Achievement	Specific Exploitation Plan	TSA
15	Development of rApps/xApps for Relay management / Building NDT	Research Achievement	Specific Exploitation Plan	UPC

4 Exploitation Plan

An adequate business and exploitation strategy is important to achieve a short- and long-term impact throughout the duration of the project and beyond. Among the main tasks to be fulfilled, the following stand out: 1) a continuous seek of innovative business models in the different areas of development especially by use case partners in their verticals, 2) a continuous market analysis and identification of novel services and applications for the considered vertical users, and 3) assurance of sustainability and viability of the solutions and of the identified business models. To properly wrap around these activities, monitoring and systematic validation of all of them are essential to ensure a high impact during and beyond the action. A special task has been set up in WP6 to track these activities. A dedicated project milestone (MS4), set at month two, reported in BeGREEN D6.1 [1], defined a plan for exploitation and dissemination of project's results. This document reports the intermediate results of implementing that plan.

The individual consortium partners, all of which are committed to contribute according to their expertise and profile, have the following ambitions for exploitation of the results of BeGREEN project:

4.1 Individual exploitation plan

4.1.1 Industrial partners

4.1.1.1 BT

BT is both the operator of the largest public mobile network in the UK under the EE brand and has a BT Enterprise division that provides telecommunications services to other commercial organisations. BT Enterprise customers include other public Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) through the supply of backhaul/fronthaul connectivity and physical base-station infrastructure provision including neutral host. In addition, a growing market for private mobile networks is targeted by BT Enterprise. As a public operator, BT will use the output of BeGREEN to minimise power cost OPERational EXpenditures (OPEX) through energy efficiency. This will be achieved, where appropriate, by influencing standards and RAN equipment vendors, selecting equipment that meets the energy efficiency capability that will be established in BeGREEN and, through the availability of the RIC, deploying algorithms capable of optimising energy efficiency for the specific BT customer base. As a supplier to public and private network operators, BT will use the knowledge gained through BeGREEN to define new connectivity and telecommunication service products, including for example the deployment of RIS. The ability to provide energy-optimised solutions for private networks will also support growth of the BT market share. BT is also hopeful of applications of BeGREEN ideas to energy-saving in home Wi-Fi, a market sector in which BT is a very big player. Specifically, the use of Wi-Fi relays improves coverage but costs energy. Ways to choose the right trade-off should emerge from BeGREEN concepts.

PROBLEM	SOLUTION	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
Energy management capabilities in O-RAN Energy management capabilities in home Wi-Fi	Integration of the BeGREEN Intelligence Plane into O-RAN architecture defining new interfaces and components	Small-cell deployments (coverage infill, indoor) with smart energy management.	Access to relevant datasets	MNOs

EXISTING ALTERNATIVES None	KEY METRICS <u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption <u>Signal properties:</u> SINR, RSRP, MCS	Home Wi-Fi relays with smart energy-efficient self-configuration.	CHANNELS BT Business Units	EARLY ADOPTERS
COST STRUCTURE TBD		REVENUE STREAMS TBD		

4.1.1.2 Telefónica (TSA)

Telefónica (TSA) plans to use the knowledge acquired from BeGREEN in the definition of the future network architectures, with the focus on provisioning novel wireless services. It will also provide a realistic overview of the maturity of the different technological components that should be available, facilitating the identification of cooperation opportunities to speed up their development. TSA plans to involve its industrial partners and stakeholders in the design of technically feasible and scalable commercial products from the project concepts. TSA will also explore new business opportunities in the private wireless networks based on positioning and cell-free network topologies, for example in factory environments or event locations.

Innovation:

Traditional MIMO has been used to improve data rate while reducing interference by creating narrow beams. However, traditional MIMO exhibits poor performance in the edge of the cell since the signal quality is limited and interference from other cells detrimentally affects the performance.

TSA provide a D-MIMO architecture and compare it with traditional MIMO to show in realistic 5G deployments how much energy an operator can save while providing better performance.

The value proposition is presented in the following VP and Lean Canvases

PROBLEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient RAN deployment complexity High CAPEX of network High OPEX of 	SOLUTION Develop new network architectures that can use power more efficiently through the use of distributed radio heads KEY METRICS	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Radio densification.	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE - CHANNELS	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> private enterprises MNOs
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<p>network</p> <p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>none</p>	<p><u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption, IDLE PC.</p> <p><u>Traffic:</u> Throughput, Max achievable throughput, CPU Load.</p> <p><u>Aggregated:</u> Bits/Joules.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturers Operators 	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Private networks</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>-</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>-</p>		

4.1.1.3 Ericsson (LMI)

Ericsson is a world leader in developing a distributed network management solution for 5G, B5G and 6G networks. In Ericsson Ireland, we are actively involved in research around B5G, 6G, orchestration, data analysis and automation. The results and knowledge which will be gained through our participation in BeGREEN will be exploited to (1) enhance internal know-how in the areas of automatic optimisations, data analytics, orchestration; (2) have a continuous role in collaborative European research projects; and (3) assess impact & improvements that we could bring towards our products.

Ericsson (LMI) will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth of its Innovation department focused on energy saving in future RAN developments. LMI have a goal to include the outcome of this project to promote energy efficiency in our development plans and new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G as well as propose new standards in energy efficiency.

We will, throughout the duration of the project, disseminate our work and results in BeGREEN internally throughout our organization. This will be done through one-to-one discussions, department-level presentations, as well as major events such as OSS Tech Day, where participants from the various sites involved in OSS development in Ericsson are invited, together with our customers.

LMI individual exploitation plan

LMI will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth of its Innovation department focused on energy saving in future RAN developments.

LMI will use the outcome of this project to promote energy efficiency in our development plans.

LMI will use the outcome of this project to promote new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G.

4.1.1.4 ARM

ARM will use BeGREEN as an Innovation platform to maximize the power saving and efficiency of current generation (5G) and learn and develop strategies for next (B5G/6G). Power saving and energy efficiency are the corner stone of ARM CPU architecture. With the learning/Blueprint/PoC achieved in BeGREEN, ARM can influence its eco-system to adhere and/or take cue from the BeGREEN research.

Strategically, while the inherent energy-efficient benefits of the ARM architecture have shown commercial promise to drive sales in the 5G/6G mobile RAN compute platform market, the competitive market offerings continue to evolve, including CPU evolutions such as Intel with their vRAN AVX processor instruction set extensions, cost-effective x86 platforms from AMD, cloud based CPU platforms like AWS Graviton, and the applicability of GPU and other DSP type hardware acceleration (like NVIDIA Grace and NXP Layerscale). One of the goals of ARM is to understand the real competitive benefits of their architecture for realistic O-RAN workloads, consistent with ARM IPR licensing to ARM platform vendors, to be able to characterize the market sizing, such as Total Addressable Market (TAM), Serviceable Available Market (SAM) and Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM), or market share, to enable strategic business unit decisions on future investments and priorities.

4.1.1.5 Parallel Wireless (PW)

PW is one of the pioneers in accelerating the global O-RAN movement, building wireless networks around the world with their in-house software and hardware solutions. BeGREEN output will be used by PW for significant simplification in terms of cost and power consumption focusing on effective solutions, specifically for the upcoming multiuser MIMO. PW intends to convert the vast majority of the PHY processing (which gets higher and higher with multiuser MIMO) to very low CPU consuming process with efficient GPU based acceleration. Accordingly, the results and based on the advanced outputs of BeGREEN, PW will develop and productize RU offload HW and SW solution (TRL9) and will make it commercially available leveraging best fit COTS GPU-based accelerators.

4.1.1.6 NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH (NEC)

NEC plans to use the results and findings from BeGREEN to improve its current RIS product prototypes and evolve its data-driven product portfolio considering the benefits of AI and ML to optimize energy efficiency for AI services. In this way, BeGREEN will have an impact on NEC’s Mobile Radio Access Networks and Mobile Wireless Networking business units, specifically, on O-RAN compliant virtualized RAN products and NEC’s advanced analytics platform for next-generation OSS. The project results will be used to demonstrate how it is possible to leverage developed innovations to optimize the energy consumption to both NEC development groups and potential customers, e.g., European network operators.

PROBLEM	SOLUTION	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
RIS integration into O-RAN RIS reconfiguration using sensing EXISTING ALTERNATIVES RIS could be reconfigured using physical layer measurements from the DU Relays could be an alternative for RIS	Integration of the RIS into the O-RAN architecture defining new interfaces and components Using ISAC metrics to reconfigure the RISs KEY METRICS <u>Power:</u> Energy, Power consumption <u>Signal properties:</u> SINR, RSRP, MCS	AI-powered energy efficient RIS control that leverages sensing and physical layer measurements to reconfigure RISs	Novel AI/ML algorithms, access to relevant datasets CHANNELS NEC Business Units	MNOs EARLY ADOPTERS Companies trying to adopt sell RIS solutions for MNOs adopting O-RAN
COST STRUCTURE		REVENUE STREAMS		
TBD		TBD		

4.1.2 Research and academic partners

4.1.2.1 I2CAT Foundation (I2CAT)

i2CAT will focus its exploitation on the O-RAN related assets developed in the project such as the O-RAN Non-RT RIC and the developed rApps for optimizing Energy Efficiency in the RAN. Market exploitation of this software assets will be pursued through license transfer agreements.

In particular, I2CAT will disseminate relevant project results to the industrial sector, starting with the members of its board of trustees that include MNOs like Orange, Vodafone, Telefonica, and Parlem, and vendors like Juniper, Cisco and Fujitsu. In addition, I2CAT will also disseminate the relevant project results to the public administration of Catalonia that is fostering policies around digitalization. I2CAT is leading the connectivity strand of the DIH4CAT¹, which is a digital innovation hub aimed at strengthening the digital competences of Catalan SME. Finally, Neutron² is an I2CAT spin off developing a cloud-based management system for private 5G network. Neutron is thus a clear recipient of some of the innovations developed in BeGREEN. Project results will also foster i2CAT participation in future calls of the SNS program.

Innovation:

i2CAT will study joint intelligent control of RAN and RIS empowered by AI/ML. To do this, i2CAT will leverage the O-RAN architecture, re-using O-RAN interfaces and components and extending them whenever needed. This may include developing xApps/rApps and the definition of new service and information models for the

¹ <https://dih4cat.cat/en/>

² <https://www.neutron.com/>

E1 and O1 interfaces.

The proposed Intelligence Plane incorporates an AI Engine, which will provide a serverless execution environment hosting the AI/ML models, offering inference and training services to the rApps/xApps by following a loosely coupled approach. This solution allows ML model developers to focus on the model implementation and optimisation, while rApp developers can work on the control logic independently of how the model will be trained and served.

I2CAT individual exploitation plan

i2CAT developments within BeGREEN are focused on two main topics, which could be exploited as an asset:

- Intelligence Plane: non-RT RIC implementation plus AI Engine to expose and facilitate AI/ML services to rApp developers. RIS Control integrated with O-RAN architecture.
- AI/ML-based RAN optimisations for energy efficiency:
 - Cell on/off control: rApp managing the on/off cycles of the cells in the RUs according to traffic predictions.
 - UPF CPU control: rApp managing the CPU state of edge COTS servers hosting UPFs according to traffic predictions.
 - RIS Control: rApp/xApp managing RIS to join coverage extension and cell on/off control.

The value proposition is presented in the following VP & Lean Canvases.

PROBLEM	SOLUTION	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
AI/ML integration into O-RAN RIS integration into O-RAN Implementation of energy efficient optimisations for O-RANs	Intelligence Plane for EE RANs with integrates AI Engine to support AI/ML services and RIS Control AI/ML-based optimisations targeting energy-efficiency through RU control, RIS control and UPF CPU control	AI-powered energy efficient RAN control that leverages CPU optimization, RU management and RIS control	Novel AI/ML algorithms, access to relevant datasets	NPN providers MNOs RIC Vendors

<p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Existing RIC implementations and AI/ML frameworks</p> <p>Relays could be an alternative for RIS</p>	<p>KEY METRICS</p> <p><u>Power</u>: Energy, Power consumption</p> <p><u>Traffic</u>: Throughput, Max achievable throughput, CPU Load.</p> <p><u>Signal properties</u>: SINR, RSRP, MCS</p> <p><u>Aggregated</u>: Bits/Joules.</p>		<p>CHANNELS</p> <p>i2CAT’s Board of trustees (industry, public sector, and academics)</p> <p>Spin-offs, venture builders</p> <p>Industrial/academic fairs</p>	<p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Companies trying to adopt innovative solutions for O-RAN</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>TBD</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>TBD</p>		

4.1.2.2 IHP - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics (IHP)

IHP will focus its exploitation on developing further the work on ISAC and integration of the developed solutions in different platforms internally available. IHP plans to exploit the results academically via its annual summer school, and lectures given at Universities in Berlin and the graduate school supporting PhD students at IHP. Resulting ISAC HW cores and SW implementations can be exploited together with the platforms via IHP's daughter company "IHP Solutions". The developed ISAC HW and SW cores will be offered to third parties for integration in their products. The acquired know-how can be used to help Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) to develop their own products, supporting ISAC, in the form of consulting services. Additionally, IHP will file patents for the patentable algorithms and architectures for ISAC developed within this project.

During this project, many PhD students and interns will be involved in research and development of different ISAC aspects and algorithms as well as implementation approaches. This will contribute significantly towards their training in this field and will be a significant step towards producing engineers prepared for development of future products supporting ISAC.

Innovation:

The innovations for IHP focus on the research for introduction of the 6G ISAC into the RAN by leveraging radar type sensing into the typical 3GPP sensing of current 4G/5G RAN. These features are already part of the 3GPP Release-19 6G use-cases and will be features of 3GPP Release-20 6G Study Items and are also gaining industry and research momentum through initiatives such as the ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) for ISAC. IHP is currently investigating paths for the potential exploitation of the work on ISAC in SNS Stream C/D projects for 2025 calls.

IHP demonstrated initial ISAC functionality in the C-Band at the EuCNC 2024 conference in Antwerp, Belgium and are also researching the innovations of combining ISAC together with RIS in indoor scenarios.

4.1.2.3 Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC)

UPC is going to exploit its participation in BeGREEN project in order to further strengthen its ability to pursue research, development and teaching activities both for its own benefit and for the benefit of its country and the EU in general. In broad terms, the obtained expertise is expected to be applied to: (i) bring the forefront of technological development into their syllabuses to educate future engineers. (ii) Carry out doctoral and post-doctoral research in areas related to the project and, thanks to the cooperation between academia and industry during the project, foster the participation in programs such as Marie Skłodowska-Curie European Industrial Doctorate to help PhD candidates step outside academia. (iii) To improve the UPC’s postgraduate and customized training courses, facilitating the convergence between research departments and public or private companies. (iv) To get aligned with the strategy for Horizon Europe 2021-2027 and stay competitive for future research initiatives in different domains (national programme, etc.).

At M12 of BeGREEN's project execution, some more detailed insight on exploitation plans can be provided, based on the work conducted in WP2, WP3 and WP4 as well as the dissemination actions already undertaken, which are associated to WP6.

From an academic perspective, there is undoubtable growing awareness and interest on sustainability and green communications. Students pursuing both the bachelor and master's degrees in Telecommunications at UPC (ETSETB-UPC) will have the chance from the academic year 2023/24 onwards to learn on such technical areas in several subjects: "5G Mobile Communications systems", "Artificial intelligence-enabled 5G networks" and "Wireless lab". The contents elaborated in these subjects leverage results and lesson learnt from BeGREEN. Furthermore, from the second term of the academic year 2023/24 onwards, a specific chapter discussing how the work in students' bachelor's and master's degrees thesis addresses sustainability aspects will be compulsory included.

Innovation:

The main scientific problems addressed concerning the relay control and management mechanisms are:

- 1) Detection of coverage holes.
- 2) Fixed relay placement.
- 3) Candidate RUE identification.
- 4) Relay activation/deactivation process.

These problems are solved through the specification of the workflows reflecting the interactions between the components of the BeGREEN architecture and the development of algorithmic solutions that make use of AI-based models when appropriate.

Concerning other fronts of exploitation, UPC is considering two promising directions: (1) Building a Network Digital Twin (NDT) leveraging the simulation environment that is being built around UPC Campus as part of BeGREEN's activities in WP2, WP3 and WP4. Such NDT could be exploited in future SNS projects and/or in industrial collaborations (e.g., on-going collaboration with Telefonica), (2) Elaboration of selected algorithmic solutions developed in WP4 as xApps/rApps in order to progress towards their implementation and practical validation. Paths for possible further exploitation include open calls from SNS Stream C/D projects, future SNS projects in 2024 or 2025 calls as well as direct transfer to some other BeGREEN's partners or external companies.

4.1.3 SME partners

4.1.3.1 Accelleran (ACC)

ACC is an SME focusing on cloud-native O-RAN network functions (Near-RT RIC and CU) and RAN integration, especially targeted toward newer private and shared RAN (neutral host) 5G networks. The eco-system developed in BeGREEN and the resultant energy-saving capabilities will enable distinct competitive advantages (in OPEX savings from energy reduction) for ACC products and solutions and hence increased SOM. This will drive both shorter-term 5G-Advanced sales (e.g., the efficient ARM and accelerated hardware, RIC xApp driven energy-saving) and longer-term 6G (with RIS, distributed MIMO) roadmap of products. Monitoring of shorter-term commercial opportunities will be a priority for an SME such as ACC. The BeGREEN results, through Total cost of Ownership (TCO) reductions, will unlock new verticals and applications for Open B5G/6G solutions, increasing TAM. Resultant BeGREEN competitive advantages will increase the SAM through improved TCO for these new verticals and as 'greener' alternatives for current verticals (like Industrial/Enterprise private networks, shared dense urban deployments, etc.).

ACC individual exploitation plan

ACC will use BeGREEN results to foster the growth on energy saving in future RAN developments. For that, ACC will work on CU / RIC HW acceleration.

ACC will develop xApps to achieve energy efficiency (RU on/off control from the Near-Real Time RIC).

The value proposition delivered by this item is analyzed by ACC and presented in the following VP & Lean Canvases.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy efficient OpenRAN deployment complexity High CAPEX of network High OPEX of network <p>EXISTING ALTERNATIVES</p> <p>Alternative is less energy efficient</p>	<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>Develop xApps / rApps on Near-Real Time / Non-Real Time RIC to add intelligence on RU power management and improve energy efficiency.</p> <p>CU / RIC HW acceleration for performance improvement and ennergy efficiency.</p> <p>KEY METRICS</p> <p><u>Power</u>: Energy, Power consumption, IDLE PC.</p> <p><u>Traffic</u>: Throughput, Max achievable throughput, CPU Load.</p> <p><u>Aggregated</u>: Bits/Joules.</p>	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>Energy efficient CU on ARM</p> <p>xApps providing energy efficient on Open-RAN.</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <p>Use of A1 / O1 interfaces for Intelligence Plane</p> <p>CHANNELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> System integrators Neutral hosts 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> private enterprises MNOs <p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>innovative companies trying to increase productivity</p>
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>Future SW Improvement</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>licenses and royalties</p>		

4.1.3.2 Gigasys Solutions (GIGASYS)

GIGASYS is an SME on wireless consultancy and R&D program management in the area of ICT. GIGASYS will use selected BeGREEN results for strengthening its consulting competency and to deliver value to its clients in the telecommunications industry across Europe. The exploitation of BeGREEN results by GIGASYS follows a three-step process: i) Identification of exploitable project results on a continuous basis by GIGASYS' key

personnel; ii) Generation of White Papers and other information items based on the identified exploitable project results; iii) Value creation for clients through discussions, follow-up research and innovation as well as consulting on emerging networks, services, and applications related to the identified exploitable project results. GIGASYS will advise its telco clients and partners via bi- and multi-lateral exchanges, targeted workshops, and community-internal White Papers. Furthermore, GIGASYS will use BeGREEN results to advise its clients on opportunities and risks arising from BeGREEN results and the impact they may have.

4.1.3.3 RunEL (REL)

REL is an SME considered a center of excellence for OFDMA technology, REL develops the Sparq-2025 family of hardware (FPGA) accelerators for 5G O-RUs and O-DUs that reduces the 5G Network latency below 1 millisecond and enable UE position measurement accuracy of 1 cm level. REL also developed an E2E 5G network that is currently being deployed in a Sport Stadium in Israel. REL participated in four Horizon 2020 projects (IoRL, 5GENESIS, Affordable 5G and 6G Brains) and was awarded the Innovation Radar award from the EU. REL will enhance the performance of its RU and DU solutions with the BeGREEN research results in terms of power radiation, power efficiency and power consumption.

Innovation:

RunEL (REL) will develop technologies and modules that will drastically improve the power efficiency of the Radio Unit (RU) in Cellular Networks

Below development will be done by REL in BeGREEN

- Develop an AI based Digital Predistortion (DPD) and Envelope Tracking (ET) algorithms
- Develop an RU RF Power Amplifier Blanking module

AI based Digital Predistortion (DPD) and Envelope Tracking (ET) algorithms

The goal is to take advantage of new Artificial Intelligence techniques to improve the performance of DPD and ET modules in the RU RF power amplifiers.

DPD Solution Description

DPD provides an effective method to linearize RF PA operation and minimize its distortion. The method is based on incorporating a nonlinear function (the inverse function of the amplifier) between the input signal and the amplifier to produce a linear output.

The DPD must adapt to PA variations with time, temperature, PA model variations/imperfections and more. Since those variations are difficult to represent with a deterministic model, an AI based model was used to perform the PA linearization.

ET Solution Description

5G OFDMA signals need to be amplified before transmission over the air with linear amplifiers to avoid distortion of the signal. The average Peak to Average Power Ratio (PAPR) of the OFDMA signal requires a Power Amplifier (PA) backoff of 10 dB to ensure linear signal amplification. This backoff means that the average PA energy efficiency lies in the 25-35 % range. Envelope Tracking (ET) is method in which the power supply voltage applied to the RF PA is continuously adjusted ensuring the PA is operating at current peak power efficiency and as a result the PA energy consumption is reduced to the average energy and its energy efficiency is multiplied.

TRL level

The TRL Levels of the AI based DPD solution and the ET solutions are TRL-3 (experimental proof of concept)

and the proof-of-concept simulation results are presented in BeGREEN D3.1 and BeGREEN D3.2.

Commercialization Plans

The AI based DPD and ET solutions are still under evaluation by the product management department at RunEL whether it can be incorporated in RunEL Radio Unit commercial product. The main question is if the Power Saving achieved by the AI based DPD and ET modules can justify the price increase due to the additional modules incorporated to the RU. A preliminary evaluation result is that the AI based DPD and ET modules will be cost effective in high Power RU products (5 Watts and Higher) rather than Small Cell products like the current Sparq-2025-SRU RunEL RU.

Radio Unit RF Power Amplifier Blanking module

The goal is to reduce the RU PA power consumption in medium and low traffic periods turning off the PA when there is no data in the downlink stream

PA Blanking Module Description

PA blanking stops the PA energy consumption for symbols without active data allocations. This is done by disconnecting the DC bias to the RU Power Amplifiers when there is no data allocated in the OFDMA symbols that needed to be transmitted in the downlink to the User Equipment (UEs) in the RU coverage area.

When resources of a layer downlink symbol have no allocated data, the related RF PA will be blanked (momentarily shut down) for the symbol duration.

To make the PA Blanking module more efficient it is required that the scheduler in the Distributed Unit (DU) will be configured in a way that it will allocate the data in the OFDMA symbols in the Frequency domain rather than the Time domain to maximize the number of symbols that can be blanked by the PA Blanking Module at any time.

TRL level

The TRL Level of the PA Blanking Module is TRL-4 (technology validated in the lab) and the initial lab test results is presented in BeGREEN D3.2.

Commercialization Plans

The PA Blanking solution was already demonstrated at the BeGREEN stand in the last EUCNC 2024 conference in Antwerp on June 2024. The PA blanking module is currently being incorporated in the RunEL Sparq-2025-SRU Radio Unit commercial product and will be provided to any new customer that will purchase the Radio.

4.1.4 Summary of individual exploitation plan

Summary of BeGREEN partners’ exploitation plans can be found in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1 Summary of BeGREEN Partners' Individual Plans

Partner	Interest in the Exploitation	Routes for Exploitation	Target Audience	Yearly Plan
ACC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop xApps to achieve RU power on/Off from RIC and work on energy efficiency. ACC will work on CU/RIC HW acceleration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop API and improve A1 and O1 interfaces. CU HW Acceleration (XDP / Security) Develop energy saving xApps 	Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2024/2025 2024

GIGASYS	Use the inspiration by BeGREEN innovations in consulting services to clients.	Broaden the consultancy area using achieved experience and knowledge from the project.	Consultancy clients	2024, 2025
IHP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of ISAC algorithms, approaches and architectures for integration in 6G networks • Using sensing information for optimizing radio network energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents in developed algorithms and licensing via daughter company “IHP Solutions” • Potential integration within other products • Training of engineers and PhD students in future sensing technologies 	Industry and academia	2024, 2025
TSA	Define future network architectures	Simulation of different network topologies in different environments	Telecom industry, industrial deployments, internal management	TBD
UPC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing sustainability & energy efficiency in syllabus at UPC • Development of rApps/xApps for Relay management • Building NDT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bachelor and Master degrees in Telecommunications Engineering at UPC • SNS JU 2024 & 2025 calls 	Academia, Telecom industry	2024, 2025
BT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy management rApps/xApps • Mathematical energy models for various network components. • System-level simulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of rApps/xApps for running on local small-cell testbed • Development of such models. • Programming these energy models in system-level simulations. • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BT wireless research staff • BT/EE network operations • BT wireless research staff • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mid-2025 • Mid-2025 • Mid-2025
NEC	RIS integration into O-RAN	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Developing an architecture to integrate RIS into O-RAN 2) Identifying the corresponding metrics to optimize RIS configuration 	NEC’s Telecom Services Business Unit	TBD
I2CAT	<p>Offer innovative RAN Intelligent Control for O-RAN.</p> <p>RIS integration into O-RAN</p>	<p>Develop RIC and AI Engine platform.</p> <p>Develop RIS Control.</p> <p>Develop rApps/xApps targeting energy efficiency.</p>	i2CAT board of trustees (private, public, academic).	TBD
REL	Offer the Green RU product developed in BeGREEN to RunEL vertical markets customers	RunEL Global Marketing and Sales Channels, Digital Media (Website and LinkedIn) and Integration partners	Global Private 5G Network operators and System integrators	2025 and on
PW	Energy saving in L1 processing algorithms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use energy efficient ARM architecture for L1 processing vs. legacy 	<p>Operators that will use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PW Products 	Using ARM: 2024

		<p>architectures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilize already existing GPUs in the system for L1 processing (e.g. GPUs which are used for other purposes such as AI) or adding dedicated GPUs. Use these GPUs for wireless performance improvement and power consumption reduction. Reducing number of required CPU cores and thus reducing the operator’s equipment footprint and capex 	<p>which are based on ARM architecture.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibly in the future: PW Products which are based on offloading some of the L1 algorithms to GPU 	<p>Using GPU: TBD</p>
LMI	Energy efficiency and energy saving in future developments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> energy saving in future RAN developments. promote new energy efficiency features in B5G and 6G 	Network Management and RAN customers	TBD

4.2 Joint exploitation plan (All partners)

4.2.1 Partners joint exploitation plan

Exploitation activities: addressing the exploitation of the project results by the various partners of the consortium, with a particular focus on joint exploitation.

Opportunities for joint exploitation of project results will be analyzed throughout the project, as part of the work in T6.4. However, the BeGREEN consortium incorporates partners that have an existing track record of collaboration, which paves the way for additional joint exploitations beyond the project lifetime.

4.2.1.1 Joint exploitation CU HW Acceleration (ACC-ARM)

CU HW acceleration is an opportunity for ACC and ARM to focus on energy efficiency and produce a valuable joint product line for different market. ACC and ARM are planning to incorporate an energy efficient server which most efficiently fits CU with (XDP / Security) different traffic scenarios. According to ACC-ARM joint exploitation plan, energy efficient CU will be tested in BeGREEN project timeframe, and first time will be disseminated during the EuCNC conference in June 2024.

This business model of ARM, however, is to license their CPU cores to CPU/SoC/system manufacturers (such as for ARM based MacBooks & smartphones), so it will be COTS server manufacturers (such as Lenovo, Dell, etc.) whose ARM based servers will be utilized in O-RAN and Telco Edge products by Accelleran. In this respect, there is indirect joint exploitation between ARM (promoting and optimizing the ARM hardware ecosystem for O-RAN) and Accelleran as a customer to bring the ARM based power-efficiencies and additional innovations to market. Beyond the pure CPU solutions, there is considerable growing market demand for AI/ML accelerated and energy efficiency solutions (such as NVIDIA who utilize ARM cores in their AI/ML accelerated TPU/DPU products) for which the O-RAN RIC and AI/ML xApps/rApps (such as the energy-plane ones being developed in BeGREEN) have increasing market applicability and will increasingly do so in the evolution towards ‘Native AI/ML’ in 6G RAN. Product line plan is for the end of 2024.

4.2.1.2 Joint exploitation DU HW Acceleration (PW-ARM)

PW and ARM are planning to offer MNOs cloud based L1 solutions which are implemented over ARM architecture in their future projects. This will help improving N/W energy efficient compared to legacy x86 solutions. The solutions will include the modules being developed within BeGREEN but also other parts of the L1 transceiver.

4.2.1.3 Joint exploitation of RIS reconfiguration using sensing metrics (IHP-NEC)

IHP and NEC aim to collaborate closely towards the use of sensing metrics for RIS reconfiguration. This strategic partnership aims to leverage the expertise of both entities to develop and refine the necessary methodologies for seamless integration of RIS reconfiguration techniques. With a shared vision, IHP and NEC recognize the immense potential of this collaboration in driving forward the capabilities of RIS technology. Through pooling their resources and knowledge, IHP and NEC intend to define robust sensing metrics that will ease and enable efficient reconfiguration of the elements of the RIS. This collaboration also seeks to streamline the deployment and management of RIS within various applications. Moreover, the joint efforts of IHP and NEC pave the way for future advancements in RIS technology, setting a standard for collaborative endeavours in the field.

4.2.1.4 Joint exploitation RIS integration into O-RAN (I2CAT-NEC)

I2CAT and NEC will joint efforts to develop the necessary interfaces for seamless integration of RIS within the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture. This collaboration focuses on innovation and interoperability, as both entities recognize the transformative potential of jointly exploiting RIS integration. By pooling their expertise and resources, I2CAT and NEC aim to define interfaces and protocols that will facilitate the seamless deployment and management of RIS elements within the O-RAN framework. This collaborative endeavour not only accelerates the adoption of RIS technology but also sets a precedent for future collaborations in EU projects.

4.2.1.5 Joint exploitation multi-vendor O-RAN (ACC-REL)

Since ACC makes the RIC and CU network functions in the dRAX product line and REL makes RUs, joint exploitation of ACC and REL products requires a 3rd party DU solution.

REL is now also investigating and starting to test the use of the srsRAN³ open-source gNB software. As ACC has ongoing project on the integration of a srsRAN DU (with F1 HLS split towards ACC CU and E2 interfacing towards ACC Near-RT RIC), this provides an avenue for ACC and REL to jointly exploit this work in an integrated multi-vendor 5G O-RAN, i.e., ACC CU, plus srsRU, plus REL RU, for future innovation and subsequent joint exploitations.

The potential for this joint exploitation is being investigated, to be further analysed and reported in BeGREEN D6.5.

4.2.1.6 Joint exploitation O-RAN Intelligence plane (ACC-I2CAT)

The Intelligence Plane developed in BeGREEN will provide a novel framework for developing AI-driven rApps/xApps and integrate them with O-RAN RICs. This could be an opportunity for Accelleran to enhance its dRAX product and for i2CAT in order to explore new license transfer agreements.

ACC and i2CAT have a long track record of collaboration in previous 5GPPP projects, which led to the integration of i2CAT RICs with Accelleran's dRAX product. Additionally, i2CAT's spin-off, Neutron, which is

³ <https://www.srsite.com/>

commercializing management systems for private 5G networks, could facilitate the joint exploitation of this asset. ACC costumers interested in enhancing dRAX framework with AI-driven rApps/xApps to optimize its network management operations would be targeted audience. Also, rApp/xApp or ML model developers (e.g., ACC or i2CAT themselves) could exploit this asset to develop novel solutions which could be applied to ACC's product or transferred to other O-RAN RIC vendors.

An example of the collaboration towards joint exploitation between ACC & i2CAT is with the FIT 5GaaS (GA 958832), where the H.2020 RIA innovations are brought to a higher TRL as a step towards exploitation. This is now actively being promoted for infrastructure deployments (such as in CEF projects) as a next step. The energy-efficiency innovations will add considerable market potential and USP (Unique Selling Points) as the market for multi-vendor O-RAN solutions still evolves.

Additionally, ACC is in discussions with Neutroon⁴ for joint commercial exploitation and further innovation of the ACC/i2CAT IPR and cooperation towards 6G in SNS proposals, with the rationale as above in that the initial market for 5G O-RAN is currently dominated by 'single vendor solutions' (being Samsung/NEC and maybe Mavenir as well as traditional major RAN vendors like Ericsson and Nokia repositioning themselves as O-RAN vendors to try and stop declining market share). The market faithful to the true principles of O-RAN, namely disaggregated and interoperable multi-vendor, is still a work-in-progress and is expected to get fully developed in the 5G-Advanced/6G timeframe, so ongoing Research and Innovation projects will still be required in the short and medium term to support the steps towards this joint exploitation.

4.2.2 Summary of joint exploitation plans

Partner	Interest in the Exploitation	Routes for Exploitation	Target Customer	Yearly Plan
ACC, ARM	ACC will work on CU/RIC HW acceleration.	CU HW Acceleration (XDP / Security)	Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence customer	2024
PW, ARM	Energy saving in L1 processing algorithms.	Use energy efficient ARM architecture for L1 processing	Operators that will use PW Products which are based on ARM architecture.	2024
IHP, NEC	Demo 2 (sensing + RIS results)	RIS reconfiguration using sensing metrics	Telecom Services Business Unit	2024
I2CAT, NEC	RIS integration into O-RAN	Integration of RIS in O-RAN	Telecom Services Business Unit	2024
ACC, REL	Multi-vendor O-RAN	REL will integrate RU to srsRAN DU and ACC CU /RIC	Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence customer	TBD
ACC, I2CAT	Provide an Intelligence Plane for enabling AI-driven optimisations in O-RAN	Integration of the Intelligence Plane and Accelleran dRAX product, development of novel rapps/xapps/ML models using the framework	Accelleran dRAX™ Open Interface RAN Intelligence customer, rApp/xApp/ML model developers, i2CAT spin-off	TBD

⁴ <https://www.neutroon.com/>

5 Updated Projections for BeGREEN Relevant Market Sizing

The BeGREEN proposal contained market estimations for the potential commercial exploitation of the developed technologies and resultant products, based on O-RAN Alliance or Open RAN standards.

This market has evolved since the writing of that proposal and this chapter presents the current and updated market estimates both for Open RAN solutions in general and more specifically ones leveraging the OPEX savings through BeGREEN energy savings and the market share addressed by products that are differentiated by energy efficiency and sustainability criteria.

5.1.1 Target Markets Addressed by BeGREEN Open RAN Solutions

The large RAN vendors (such as Ericsson, Nokia, Huawei), while initially hostile or at least ambivalent to Open RAN, seeing it as a threat to their market share, have increasingly started to adopt these technologies in their products (or at least their marketing).

This, together with real issues of multi-vendor product interoperability and complications of 'RAN integration', has seen the emergence of the 'Single Open RAN vendors' terminology, targeted towards traditional Public MNOs (or Telcos) customers.

This has also seen a big rise of newer Asian vendors (especially NEC of Japan and Samsung of Korea) leveraging this to enhance their market share in these traditional MNO markets.

However, for new and smaller vendors, the primary market for Open RAN products and solutions is for the emerging 'Private 5G' (or NPN: Non-Public Networks) for new vertical applications such as manufacturing, industrial, mining and other B2B (Business to Business) types of markets, with services provisioned either 'do it yourself' SNPN, through newer CSP (Communication Service Providers) or SI (System Integrators) or through established MNO looking to expand from purely consumer B2C to also B2B service offerings (typically with higher margins).

These 'Private 5G' networks have initially been truly private (SNPN) for initial 'richer' verticals, where cost is not a major consideration, but it is increasingly evolving towards Shared Private 5G (using neutral host RAN sharing or sharing of Public networks PNI-NPN), where the affordability imperative drives the business plans.

5.1.2 General Open RAN Solution Market Sizing

The market for private and shared RAN networks based on Open RAN technologies is expected to grow rapidly. In 2024, the Open RAN market is valued at approximately **USD 2.8 billion**. Projections indicate this market will expand at a **compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 39.4%**, reaching **USD 20.9 billion by 2030** [17] [18].

This growth is driven by factors such as increased **adoption of 5G networks**, the demand for greater **network flexibility**, and **multi-vendor ecosystems** that reduce the cost of deploying and operating mobile networks [18]. Open RAN solutions align well with cloud-native architectures, further accelerating adoption in both **private networks and hybrid cloud deployments** [19].

By **2033**, the Open RAN market could grow to **USD 32 billion**, supported by ongoing regulatory efforts and collaborative industry initiatives to promote open standards and vendor diversification [20] [21]. The rising popularity of **greenfield deployments**, which allow providers to build new infrastructure using best-in-class technology, is also fueling market growth. These deployments emphasize **vendor flexibility** and encourage innovation in building future-oriented networks [17, 19].

5.1.3 Projected Market Sizing of BeGREEN enabled OPEX savings through Energy Efficiency

The primary benefits of the BeGREEN innovations is reduction of energy consumption, leading to Open RAN OPEX (Operational Expenditure) reduction, hence TOC (Total Cost of Ownership).

In mobile networks based on 3GPP standards, **15-40%** of the **Operational Expenditure (OPEX)** is attributed to energy costs, primarily due to the power consumption of Radio Access Network (RAN) elements, such as base stations. This percentage varies depending on the network architecture, technology generation (e.g., 4G, 5G), and the deployment environment. RAN is the largest consumer of energy within the network, accounting for up to **60-70% of the total energy consumption** in many cases [22] [23] [24] [25].

Operators are adopting energy-saving technologies, such as AI-driven traffic optimization and sleep-mode functions, to reduce energy expenditures. The increasing deployment of Open RAN technologies also provides new opportunities to enhance energy efficiency by enabling more flexible and dynamic network management through multi-vendor environments [24] [25].

Quantifying the impact of adopting **advanced O-RAN-based energy savings** on the **Total Addressable Market (TAM)**, **Serviceable Available Market (SAM)**, and **Serviceable Obtainable Market (SOM)** requires assessing the extended market potential created through energy efficiency, reduced operating costs, and increased scalability. Below is an analysis of the projected market increases:

5.1.3.1 TAM Increase

The **TAM** represents the total market potential for O-RAN-based solutions. With traditional 3GPP networks expected to expand but facing cost limitations due to energy demands, introducing advanced energy-saving solutions—such as ML-based traffic steering and dynamic load management—creates additional TAM.

- **Impact:** The Open RAN market is projected to grow from **USD 2.8 billion in 2024 to USD 20.9 billion by 2030**, at a **CAGR of 39.4%** [17] [18].
- **Quantification:** Energy-efficient features are likely to increase TAM by an additional **10-15%** beyond baseline growth, as these solutions attract enterprises focused on green technology, smart cities, and 5G industrial use cases [26] [27].

5.1.3.2 SAM Increase

The **SAM** reflects the portion of the TAM that is realistically serviceable based on infrastructure and deployment feasibility. With energy-saving strategies, operators can unlock more cost-effective deployments and address regions and use cases previously unviable due to high energy costs.

- **Impact:** By adopting **O-RAN energy-efficient strategies**, the SAM could increase by **15-20%** as operators can tap into new energy-conscious sectors, such as **private 5G networks**, **smart manufacturing**, and **critical infrastructure** [28] [27]. Reduced operational costs also allow operators to deploy networks in remote and underserved areas, further expanding the SAM.

5.1.3.3 SON Increase

The **SOM**, or market share, reflects the actual portion of the SAM that operators can capture. Advanced O-RAN energy savings improve network efficiency and competitiveness, which translates into higher market penetration.

- **Impact:** According to industry reports, operators adopting advanced O-RAN energy-saving technologies may achieve **10-20% higher market share** than those relying solely on traditional 3GPP solutions [26] [27].
- **Quantification:** The improved cost structure and energy efficiency provide a competitive advantage

in both consumer and enterprise segments, likely resulting in a **5-10% incremental market share gain** across key 5G services [27].

5.1.3.4 Summary

Incorporating **advanced BeGREEN O-RAN-based energy savings** can drive:

1. **TAM Increase:** 10-15% additional growth by expanding into new sectors and use cases.
2. **SAM Increase:** 15-20% expansion by reducing deployment costs and enabling access to previously unserved markets.
3. **SOM Increase:** 10-20% higher market share due to competitive advantages and enhanced cost efficiency.

6 Summary and Conclusions

This document reported the consortium's interim exploitation results, as defined in the plan outlined in BeGREEN D6.1 [1].

These exploitation results are intended to maximize the impact of the project and to ensure the fulfilment of the BeGREEN exploitation objectives. Although these plans are subject to modifications, they constitute the framework of reference that will drive the coordination, implementation, supervision and maximization of BeGREEN exploitation activities. Also, they ensure that BeGREEN achievements are widely spread over the BeGREEN target audience to enhance the project's impact and visibility to the European Union (EU) and the entire world.

BeGREEN's IM will continue monitoring project's exploitation activities toward achieving its objectives. The final report on project's exploitations is expected at the end of the project in BeGREEN D6.5.

The exploitation goals and exploitable results of BeGREEN are consistent with the scope of the project SNS Stream A call SNS-2022-STREAM-A-01-01, of type RIA action, with results typically of TRL 3-4 (with some limited results of TRL 5) maturity, with significant additional innovation and commercialization efforts required, beyond the results of this project, for true commercial exploitation.

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